

**INTRUSION DETECTION:
A BIBLIOGRAPHY OF ONE DECADE (1993-2003)¹**

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Contenido

1. Intrusion Detection in 1993
2. Intrusion Detection in 1994
3. Intrusion Detection in 1995
4. Intrusion Detection in 1996
5. Intrusion Detection in 1997
6. Intrusion Detection in 1998
7. Intrusion Detection in 1999
8. Intrusion Detection in 2000
9. Intrusion Detection in 2001
10. Intrusion Detection in 2002
11. Intrusion Detection in 2003

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7. INTRUSION DETECTION IN 1999

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8. INTRUSION DETECTION IN 2000

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